

LINKNOVATE STARTUP RADAR – DATALIFE USE CASE

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ABSTRACT

STARTUP RADAR (SR) is one of the latest Linknovate R&D efforts.

SR automatically extracts semantic relations between entities from unstructured and heterogeneous data sources. SR aims at detecting 3 critical events from over 80M documents present in Linknovate's (LKN) database, including news and other unstructured text sources:

1. Mergers & acquisitions
2. Funding events and
3. Product launches

The second capability, which we focus on in this use-case, is a recommendation system to locate "Similar To" companies based on their know-how, products and "innovation weak signals". Current providers usually rely on financial figures, type of funding round (e.g., series A), number of employees, geographic location, etc. But some of the most exciting info for the user relies on what these companies actually do and know.

SR enables investors and innovation professionals (e.g., innovation directors, R&D managers, new product development teams, etc) to compare companies and conduct tech due diligence, allowing them to make better-informed investment decisions. SR aims to fill the gap for investors, accelerators, and seed funds who lack the data analysis capabilities for tech benchmarking that bigger funds have by manually curating data and relying on their heavy networks. With its automation SR aims to save time, increase deal flow, and enhance the technology due diligence capabilities of our users, by the superior discovery of similar companies (and the future work in relation extraction for the detection of relations and events in unstructured text, e.g., in news).

While competitors like Crunchbase and ChatGPT (OpenAI) exist, they lack precision and recall, since the former lacks "background data" on innovation "weak signals" for the companies of study, and the latter relies -by design- on the overall signals of a startup (website, blog posts, social media, etc) and its marketing jargon rather than robustly comparing innovation signals, apart from not necessarily being up to date.

NEED

SR aims to support mainly the Investor community who demand software tools to enhance their deal flow and technology due diligence. SR can get more intelligence about startups and companies that are "tech-driven" to dramatically improve your company technology and startup radar.

The key points of the SR proposal are:

1. Relation extraction about products, financing and M&A events from unstructured text data sources, which is a very complex challenge. Thus, SR is able to maintain up-to-date structured info about these events.
2. Capability to compare companies and help with tech due diligence: what alternative companies should I consider investing in, how my potential invested company compares (from a tech perspective) with others, how does the tech landscape look like (Similar companies).

Investors (VC, hedge funds, etc) and foremost angels, accelerators, and seed funds lack the data analysis capabilities to quickly and effortlessly benchmark from a tech perspective the companies they (consider) invest in. It is a manual analyst driven work, and the funds with less human resources oftentimes rely on their own investee analysis.

For innovation professionals, it is important to gather "similar organization" data in order to have a more complete understanding of the tech landscape and the startups in their fields of interest. This intelligence is usually more complete from a business perspective, but not from a tech perspective, which is ever evolving (i.e., it demands staying up to date and monitoring changes after a certain period of time).

BENEFITS

The main benefits that SR aims to offer the users are:

- Save time: Reduce the time spent on the startup research process.
- Superior discovery capability of similar companies based on expertise and/or products.
- Help do a better technology due diligence (tech DD): automate technology due diligence of startups and systematize the process can help investors have a clear market landscape in emerging industries (especially those with high growth & evolution).
- Increase deal flow (for investors): by optimizing their processes and boosting better informed decisions.

COMPETITORS AND HOW IT IS SOLVED TODAY

Crunchbase is a business information platform (particularly focusing on startups) that provides data and insights on companies, including their funding, industry, and key personnel. Their "Similar Companies" feature analyzes various data points such as industry, funding, and market presence to suggest companies that share similarities with a given company:

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Figure 1: Screenshot of a service competing with Startup Radar, Crunchbase.

CB lacks precision because they rely mainly on the similarity of their generic industry/topic. Additionally, they rely mostly on its funding stage and employee's data, which are not necessarily the best parameters.

As we can see in the previous example, Crunchbase is suggesting the marketplace Pachama as a similar company to Linknovate (a tech scouting platform) because both are categorized as "artificial intelligence" companies, a very wide topic.

Another recent alternative is ChatGPT, a powerful language model designed for context-aware conversations, providing detailed and coherent responses to a wide range of queries and prompts. ChatGPT's ability to find similar companies to a given one is based on matching marketing jargon rather than robustly comparing innovation signals like the LKN approach, making it less suitable for "hard-core tech" comparisons.

Figure 2: Screenshot of a prompt in chatGPT to get the competing companies for Linknovate.

This problem can be solved also manually by using Google or other generic search engines, but it requires a much longer time of manual analysis. Furthermore, it is important to understand how to set up the search to get

right results and the analyst needs a good knowledge of the topic under study to make her final selection.

Figure 3: Screenshot of a service competing with Startup Radar, Startup Ranking [1]

Figure 4: Screenshot of a service competing with Startup Radar, Owler.

Figure 5: Screenshot of a service competing with Startup Radar, Tracxn [2]

Figure 6: Screenshot of a service competing with Startup Radar, 6sense [3]

As it can be observed the precision and recall of these solutions is insufficient, presenting companies that are somehow in the same (generic) field: research, business intelligence, or simply AI; and other times simply missing the target.

Finally, organizations may depend on their internal networks and the self-assessment of the startup/organization they are considering for investment, while larger companies could seek assistance from their network of consultants, university professors, and academics.

APPROACH

Similarity explanation

During the SR project, we tested with real use case owners 4 different types of explanations. All of them are text-based explanations. Following [4] we opted for two approaches: full natural language and keyword (tag) based. Previous results in the field of movie recommendation demonstrated that textual descriptions were more appropriate for the user than tag-based explanations, but we wanted to test in our particular use case. So finally, we tested:

- **Brief company description:** Describe each one of the matched companies with a few sentences extracted from the Linknovate profile description.
- **Keywords:** These keywords are chosen based on their relevance to the matching process of the two companies and they should be a quick overview of their know-how.
- **Extractive Summaries:** Text extractions from a couple of documents (patent, research publication...) associated with both matched companies (one for each), which talks about a common topic, indicative of their main knowledge and activity.
- **Abstractive Summaries:** Key information is extracted from a couple of documents and new sentences are generated from it to create a summary.

Based on the scores and comments of the approached testers, the option that is more useful for them is the one based on the company description.

Figure 7: Average beta tester scores for each type of proposed explanation

The company's description has the correct amount of information to earn trust from users making them happier with the suggestion. In other words, they are short and clear enough to understand in a few sentences if two companies are similar or not. The keywords approach has a good acceptance as well, because it is a straight way to communicate key information to users. So, we understand that a combination of both could be a great solution to explain the recommendations to the users.

Companies like Netflix have also demonstrated [5] the importance of graphical representations when recommending items to users. Therefore, we additionally designed a visual proposal to provide a clear and intuitive explanation.

Figure 8: Example of Chord similarity graph draft supported by textual explanations

This Chord diagram [6] visualizes the similarity strengths between the anchor company (here: Pilot photonics) and its four most similar companies (here: Eblana, Chromacity, EFFECT Photonics, and Aegiq). The thickness of the arrows connecting two companies represents the similarity level between the anchor company and its match.

Step 1: Select the company to be analyzed

As the analyst begins to type the name, the tool suggests companies with profiles on the platform which match that name:

Figure 9: Screenshot of the selection process of the organization to be analyzed in Startup Radar

If there is no match on the platform, it allows for new company creation, just by providing the company's name and website - for later crawling and adding info to the newly generated company profile, and LKN enriching procedures from LKN data sources (like patents, scientific publications, grants, etc).

This information will be the support in the subsequent recommendation of suggested similar companies.

Once the desired company profile is selected, "Search" is the next step.

Step 2 – Indicate the innovation area

The analyst indicates in SR the innovation area of interest for the company under study.

This area of innovation will be expressed as "search terms" in the form of keywords.

Figure 10: Search terms configuration in Startup Radar

The analyst can use the operator AND (to combine different keywords), the operator OR (to include synonyms) and other punctuation (e.g., quotation marks for key-phrases) to get more specific search results.

Step 3 – Similar organizations

Based on the selected company and the innovation area indicated as keywords, SR offers a list of similar organizations:

Figure 11: Selection process of similar organizations in Startup Radar

The platform shows the company list ordered by relevance based on an internal score. In this way, the analyst can see first the most relevant suggested companies. This list can be ranked by company size, country, etc.

The analyst can individually select/deselect each suggested company using the icon to the left of its name, in order to add them to her study. She can also manually add similar companies not included in the tool's suggestion list, by typing in the text box in the upper left corner and selecting it (if it does not exist, it can be created as in step 1).

Step 4 – Customized Recommendations

After confirming the previous list selection, the tool generates a set of possible recommendations in the indicated area of innovation based on these selected similar organizations:

Figure 12: Recommended actions/documents selection in Startup Radar

The analyst can select the desired innovation actions (documents) by clicking on the associated “tag” field for each one of them and selecting the suggested label (automatically generated) with the name of the ongoing study.

The analyst can check more details about any of the actions/documents by clicking on the title and going to the original source.

All the selected recommendations are saved as future suggestions for the next analysis about companies in the same area of innovation.

Step 5 – Tagging and export

The innovation actions/documents selected by the analyst will be labelled with the automatically created descriptive name:

Figure 13: Tagged actions/documents to be included in the ongoing Startup Radar report

At the end of the analysis, an automatic report can be generated with all of them, in order to share this report with the company under study.

The use case relies on open source technologies. For the relation extraction tasks, we opted to utilize spaCy, a Python-based framework, to train a model using our proprietary data. Regarding the company similarity task, we constructed the recommendation system by employing Elasticsearch as the foundation for our similarity calculations. Utilizing the unique characteristics of our data, we harnessed Elasticsearch's capabilities to identify distinctive and descriptive terms within the company documents, enabling us to rank similar companies.

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